
MEDICINAL PLANT RESOURCES: MANIFESTATION AND PROSPECTS OF LIFE-SUSTAINING HEALTHCARE SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants are the principal health care resources for the majority of people all over the world. The healing properties of herbal medicines have been recognized in many ancient cultures. The traditional medical systems such as Ayurveda, Siddha and Unani are part of a time-tested culture and honored by people still today. Pharmaceutical importance of plants has led to the discovery and adoption of plant extracts which were commonly used in traditional medicine, as alternative source of remedy. A vast diversity of herbal ingredients, major proportion of which is derived from wild, provide the resource base to the herbal industry. Despite the increasing use of medicinal plants, their future, seemingly, is being threatened by complacency concerning their conservation. Global demand for herbal medicines is accompanied by dwindling supply of medicinal plants due to over-harvesting, habitat loss and agricultural encroachment. As millions of rural households use plants for self-medication community involvement in monitoring use and status of medicinal plants can contribute to effective strategies for their sustainable use.

KEYWORDS – Medicinal Plants, Sustainability, indigenous knowledge, Phytomedicines

INTRODUCTION

Human life and knowledge of preserving it as a going concern must have come into being almost simultaneously. All known cultures of the past - Egyptian, Babylonian, Jewish, Chinese, Indus-valley etc. had their own glorious and useful systems of medicine and health care. Herbal medicines also called botanical medicines or phytomedicines, refer to the use of any plant seed, berries, roots, leaves, bark or flower for medicinal purpose. Early herbalists believed that the plant part resembling any part of human body was considered useful for the ailments of those parts, and there is no part of body without its corresponding herb, a hypothesis known as the, "Doctrine of Signature" (Baquar, 2001). The economic significance of medicinal plants stems from the fact that the number of patients suffering from chronic ailments is on the rise and drugs from medicinal plants are proving to be more effective in treating such disorders (Deshpande *et al.*, 2006).

Plants are utilized as therapeutic agents since time immemorial in both organized (Ayurveda, Yunani) and unorganized (folk, tribal, native) form (Girach *et al.*, 2003). The widespread use of herbal remedies and healthcare preparations, as those described in ancient texts such as the Vedas and the Bible, and obtained from commonly used traditional herbs and medicinal plants, has been traced to the occurrence of natural products with medicinal properties (Hoareau & DaSilva, 1999). Medicinal and aromatic plants (MAPs) are produced and offered in a wide variety of products, from crude materials to processed and packaged products like pharmaceuticals, herbal remedies, teas, spirits, cosmetics, sweets, dietary supplements, varnishes and insecticides (Ohrmann, 1991; Gorecki, 2002; Lange, 1996). Herbal medicine is still the mainstay of about 75–80% of the world's population, mainly in developing countries, for primary health care because of better cultural acceptability, better compatibility with the human body and lesser side effects. It is estimated that approximately one quarter of prescribed drugs contain plant extracts or active ingredients obtained from or modelled on plant substances. Aspirin, atropine, artemisinin, colchicine, digoxin, ephedrine, morphine, physostigmine, pilocarpine, quinine, quinidine, reserpine, taxol, tubocurarine, vincristine and vinblastine are a few important examples of what medicinal plants have given us in the past. Most of these plant-derived drugs were originally discovered through the study of traditional cures and folk knowledge of indigenous people and some of these could not be substituted despite the enormous advancement in synthetic chemistry. (ICMPHD, 2010). Nature has produced wonderfully complex molecules that no synthetic chemist could ever dream up (Brower, 2008). Loss of the indigenous knowledge has been aggravated by the expansion of modern education which has made the younger generation underestimate its traditional values.

Global Potential of Plant-Based Medicines:

The high cost of modern medicines (mostly imported), their unavailability in remote areas and most importantly, the serious side effects of certain drugs, have resulted in a significant return to traditional medicine (Chapman & Chomchalow, 2004). The global market value of pharmaceuticals derived from genetic resources is estimated at US\$ 75 000–150 000 million annually (UNDP, UNEP, World Bank and WRI, 2000). The demand for medicinal plant based raw materials is growing at the rate of 15 to 25% annually, and according to an estimate of WHO, the demand for medicinal plants is likely to increase more than US \$5 trillion in 2050. In India, the medicinal plant-related trade is estimated to be approximately US \$1 billion per year (Joshi *et al.*, 2004). According to an estimate, the quantity of export of Ayurvedic products produced in India has tripled between last two financial years (2001–2002 and 2002–2003) (Kala *et al.*, 2006). China, which harvests an estimated 80% of its medicinal plant material from wild sources, exports an estimated 32,600 tons of medicinal raw material each year (Parrotta, 2002). So far, of the 2,50,000 to 3,00,000 plant species on earth only 7% of the vascular flora have been exploited for their medical potential (Iverson, 1988). About 100 plant species are involved in 25% of all drugs prescribed in advanced countries (Comer and Debus, 1996). More than 8000 plant species are known for their medicinal properties in the Asia-Pacific and about 10% of them are used regularly, mostly collected from wild. For example, it has been estimated that not less than 7500 species of medicinal plants exist in the Indonesian archipelago, of which only about 187 species are used as basic materials in traditional medicines industries (Hamid & Sitepu, 1990). In China, over 4000 species of medicinal plants have been reported (Ayensu, 1996). In India, about 90% of the total medicinal plants provide raw materials for the herbal pharmaceuticals, which are collected from the wild habitats (Rajasekharan and Ganeshan, 2002). About 2000 medicinal plants species are reported from Malaysia (Latif, 1997), while in another account 1200 species have been reported to have potential pharmaceutical value, some of which are being used as herbal medicines (Kadir, 1997).

Africa is a rich source of medicinal plants. Perhaps, the best known species is *Phytolacca dodecandra*. Extracts of the plant, commonly known as end, are used as an effective molluscicide to control schistosomiasis (Lemma, 1991). Other notable examples are *Catharanthus roseus*, which yields anti-tumour agents such as vinblastine and vincristine; and *Ricinus communis*, which yields the laxative--castor oil. In Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia and South Africa, *Harpagophytum procumbens* is produced as a crude drug for export. Similarly, *Hibiscus sabdariffa* is exported from Sudan and Egypt. Other exports are *Pausinystalia yohimbe* from Cameroon, Nigeria and Rwanda, which yields *yohimbine*; and *Rauwolfia vomitoria*, from Madagascar, Mozambique and Zaire, which is exploited to yield reserpine and ajmaline. The use of medicinal plants like *Eupatorium perfoliatum* (bonest), *Podophyllum peltatum* (mayapple), and *Panax quinquefolium* (ginseng) in the USA has long been associated with the American Indians. These plants have also been appreciated and recognised for their aesthetic and ornamental value. In Central America medicinal plants have been widely used - by the *Maya* Indians in Mexico, the *Miskitos* and *Sumus* in Honduras and Nicaragua, the *Pech*, *Lencas*, and *Xicaques* in Honduras, the *Pipiles* in El Salvador, the *Talamancas* in Costa Rica, and the *Guaymis* and *Kunas* in Panama (Hoareau & DaSilva, 1999).

In Europe, some 1500 species of medicinal and aromatic plants are widely used in Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Spain, Turkey, and the United Kingdom. The Maltese islands constitute an apt example where medicinal plants are widely used in everyday life as part of folk medicinal remedies (Lanfranco, 1992).

In Asia, there are large-scale programs of commercial production, while in other regions; activity is more piecemeal and on a demonstration project basis. Critical factors influencing regional development are the presence or absence of policy awareness, the volume of international trade in medicinal plants, and a significant absence of dedicated funding to catalyze such action. Regional and international issues have been identified and responded to by major institutional actors:

- ❖ The IUCN Medicinal Plant Study Group has focused on the identification, management and protection of regionally and globally threatened species;
- ❖ TRAFFIC and CITES focus on the monitoring and regulation of international trade;
- ❖ WWF and the Rainforest Alliance promote education and the regulation of international production-to-consumption chains, e.g. via certification schemes;
- ❖ WWF, People and Plants, IDRC, and others concentrate on the development of capacity and best practices.

The Global Environment Facility (GEF) appears to be the leading source of international support for broad-based programmatic development. Of at least eight GEF medicinal plant conservation projects, four are in Africa (Egypt, Ethiopia, Ghana, Zimbabwe), one is in the Eastern Mediterranean region (Jordan), two are in Asia (India and Sri Lanka) and one multi-country project is in the Caribbean. The surge in global demand for herbal medicines has been followed by a belated growth in international awareness about the dwindling supply of the world's medicinal plants. Over-harvesting for commercial purposes, destructive harvesting practices, habitat loss resulting from forest degradation and agricultural encroachment have all been recognized as contributing factors. Recent policy interest in the importance of traditional medicine in meeting the health needs of indigenous peoples, rural communities and the poor throughout the developing world has underscored the significance of this topic for the health of the poor and indigenous groups as well as in meeting the pluralistic health requirements of more affluent consumers internationally (Bodeker, 2005).

Status of Medicinal Plant in India:

India is one of the 12 mega biodiversity centers having 45,000 plant species; its diversity is unmatched due to the 16 different agro climatic zones, 10 vegetative zones, and 15 biotic provinces. The country has a rich floral diversity (Samy & Gopalakrishnakone, 2007). There is a vast indigenous knowledge on the use of medicinal plants. Of the estimated 300 million indigenous people all over the world, about 67.7 million tribal people belonging to 573 tribal groups with various subsistence patterns have been reported from India, and it accounts for nearly 22% of world's tribal population (Arora, 1995). In India, about 2500 species are used for medicinal purposes by the different folk and tribal communities (Rajasekharan and Ganeshan, 2002). The Himalayas including North East India harbor about 8,000 plant species of which 2,500 (21.3%) have been reported to have important medicinal properties (Trivedi, 2002). For the Indian Himalayan Region, a total of 1748 species of medicinal plants - 1020 herbs, 338 shrubs, 339 trees, apart from 51 pteridophytes - have been listed. These include several of the endangered medicinal plant species. Some examples of the endangered Himalayan medicinal plant species include: *Aconitum balfourii*, *A. deinoorrhizum*, *Acorus calamus*, *Angelica glauca*, *Atropa belladonna*, *Berberis kashmiriana*, *Coptis teeta*, *Dioscorea deltoidea*, *Gentiana kurrooa*, *Nardostachys grandiflora*, *Picrorhiza kurrooa*, *Podophyllum hexandrum*, *Saussurea costus*, *Sweria chirayita* and *Taxus baccata* subsp. *wallichiana*; and the sub-tropical/sub temperate species *Aquilaria malaccensis* (Samant *et al.*, 1998).

In India, nearly 9,500 registered herbal industries and a multitude of unregistered cottage-level herbal units depend upon the continuous supply of medicinal plants for manufacture of herbal medical formulations based on Indian Systems of Medicine. In addition to the industrial consumption, significant quantities of medicinal plant resources are consumed in the country under its traditional health care practices at the household level, by traditional healers and by practitioners of Indian Systems of Medicine. An idea about the richness and diversity of these health care practices in India can be had from the diversity of plant species used in these systems (Ved & Goraya, 2007). The use and potential of some Indian Medicinal Plants has been presented in Table-1.

Table 1: Use and Potential of Selected Indian Medicinal Plants

Plant name	Commonest Ayurvedic usage	Therapeutic potential
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Kasashwasaghna (Antitussive)	Antituberculosis, Haemostatic
<i>Aloe vera</i>	Kushtaghna (Skin diseases), Agnidagdha vrana (Burns)	Antidiabetic
<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Shothaghna (Anti inflammatory), Grahaghna (Anti spasmodic)	Immunomodulator
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Smritiprada (Memory-enhancing), Kushtaghna (Skin diseases)	Antiaging
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Pramehaghna (Anti-diabetic), Kandooghna (Anti pruritic), Vranapaha (Wound healing)	Cancer Prevention
<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i>	Stanya (Galactogogue)	Anticonjunctivitis
<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	Vrushya (Aphrodisiac)	Antiparkinsonism
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Pratishyayahara (Anti cold)	Anticancer
<i>Picrorrhiza kurroa</i>	Kamalahara (Anti-jaundice)	Lipid-lowering
<i>Piper longum</i>	Shwasakasahara (Anti asthmatic)	Antimalarial
<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>	Mehaghna (Anti-diabetic)	Antiinflammatory
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Anulomana (Mild laxative)	Medhya
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Ashmarighna (Litholytic)	Antiprostatism
<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i>	Medoghna (Lipid lowering), Stanya (Galactogogue)	Antidiabetic

Source: Vaidya & Devasagayam, 2007

interest in the exploitation of medicinal and aromatic plants as pharmaceuticals, herbal remedies, flavourings, perfumes and cosmetics, and other natural products has greatly increased in the recent years (Anon., 1994; Ayensu, 1996; Salleh *et al.*, 1997; Kumar *et al.*, 2000). There are a number of Institutes/Universities in India involved in research on herbal drugs and medicinal plants (Table 2). These Institutes carry out basic and clinical research on the potential health benefits of herbal drugs.

Table 2: Herbal Research Institute/Centres in India

Name	City
CCRAS (Central Council for Research in Ayurveda and Siddha)	New Delhi
RRL (Regional Research Laboratory) (CSIR)	Jammu-Tawi
NBRI (National Botanical Research Institute) (CSIR)	Lucknow
Gujarat Ayurveda University	Jamnagar
Bhavan's SPARC	Mumbai
National Institute of Ayurveda	Jaipur
ACARTS	Mumbai
Arya Vaidya Shala	Kottakal
Interdisciplinary School of Health Sciences	Pune
Banaras Hindu University	Varanasi
CIMAP (Central Institute for Medicinal and Aromatic Plants)	Lucknow
ICMR (Indian Council for Medical Research)	New Delhi
National Medicinal Plants Board	New Delhi
Indian Drug Manufacturers	Mumbai
Regional Medical Research Centre (ICMR)	Belgaum
PERD Centre (Pharmaceutical Education and Research Development)	Ahmedabad
CCRUM (Central Council for Research in Unani Medicine)	New Delhi
NISCOM (National Institute of Science Communication)	New Delhi
IMPCOPS (Indian Medical Practitioners Co-operative Pharmacy & Stores Ltd.)	Chennai
IHMMR (Indian Institute of History of Medicine and Medical Research)	New Delhi
Zandu Foundation	Mumbai
Pharmexcil	Hyderabad
Chemexcil	Mumbai
CDRI (Central Drug Research Institute) (CSIR)	Lucknow
IMPLANT Centre (Inter-university Medicinal Plant Laboratory for Analysis, Nurture and Therapeutics)	Rajkot
NIMHANS (National Institute for Mental health and Neurosciences)	Bangalore
Panjab University	Chandigarh
LM College of Pharmacy	Ahmedabad
NBPGR (National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources)	New Delhi
NPRC (Nicholas Piramal Research Centre)	Mumbai
NCL (National Chemical Laboratory)	Pune
TBGRI (Tropical Botanical Garden & Research Institute)	Thiruvantapuram
BHU (Banaras Hindu University)	Varanasi
Podar Hospital	Mumbai
Botanical Survey of India	Kolkata
FRHLT (Foundation for Revitalisation of Local Health Traditions)	Bangalore
IASTAM (International Association for the Study of Traditional Asian Medicine)	Mumbai
ADMA (Ayurvedic Drug Manufacturing Association)	Mumbai

Source: Vaidya & Devasagayam, 2007

Though India has rich biodiversity, the growing demand is putting a heavy strain on the existing resources causing a number of species to be either threatened or endangered category. In India, less than 10% of the medicinal plants traded in the country are cultivated, about 90% are collected from the wild, very often in a destructive and unsustainable manner (Natesh, 2000). This poses a definite threat to the genetic stocks and to the diversity of medicinal plants. Recently some rapid assessment of the threat status of medicinal plants using IUCN designed CAMP methodology revealed that about 112 species in southern India, 74 species in Northern

and Central India and 42 species in the high altitude of Himalayas are threatened in the wild (Sharma *et al.*, 2010).

Cultivation of Medicinal Plants:

Medicinal plants are natural resources as they are unique, indispensable and an estimate of their availability is complex. These provide a good source of income if cultivated aggressively and traded, as the demand is fast increasing. In the quest for earning better returns from the land, farmers have been resorting to cultivation of medicinal and aromatic plants instead of conventional agriculture (Chatterjee, 2002). Cultivation is vital for the conservation of many medicinal plants, with gene banks and botanic gardens contributing to the conservation of species diversity. Plantations and corporate farming modes offer local farmers little control over what is grown, how it is grown and the price at which it is sold. Emerging cooperative models enable groups of farmers to sell direct to manufacturers and receive a fair price for produce and a dividend on profits of the cooperative. There is a need to improve basic knowledge about cultivation practices and dissemination of plant species; promote conservation of vulnerable species at the grass-roots level; adopt sustainable collection and management practices on public lands; and link the management and conservation of medicinal plants with their commercial development (Bodeker, 2005).

In order to initiate systematic cultivation of medicinal and aromatic plants high yielding varieties have to be selected. In the case of wild plants, their demonstration would require careful development work. Sometimes high yielding varieties have also to be developed by selective breeding or clonal micro propagation. The selected propagation materials have to be distributed to the farmers either through nurseries or seed banks. Systematic cultivation needs specific cultural practices and agronomical requirements. These are species specific and are dependent on soil, water and climatic conditions. Hence research and development work has to be done to formulate Good Agricultural Practices (GAP) which should include proper cultivation techniques, harvesting methods, safe use of fertilizers and pesticides and waste disposal (Joy *et al.*, 1998). The medicinal plants sector can be improved if the agricultural support agencies would come forward to help strengthen the medicinal plants growers, and if research institutions would help the plant growers by improving their basic knowledge about cultivation practices (Prajapati *et al.*, 2003).

Processing and Utilization:

The developer of a potent natural product penicillin, Nobel-laureate Ernst Boris Chain wrote an inspiring article entitled "The quest for new biodynamic substances". In 1967, he wrote, "In China and India there has been an extensive drive aimed at the systemic study of medicinal plants traditionally used in these countries in folklore medicine; this has failed, so far, to bring to light new classes of compounds with interesting pharmacologic activities. As far as drug research is concerned, therefore, we cannot expect many major surprises to come from the study of plant constituents". Practitioners of traditional medicine believe that the constituents of plants are unique as they contain both active ingredients and "non-active" components that play a role in enhancing the well-being of their patients. A rekindled interest in the pharmaceutical importance of plants have led to the discovery and adoption of plant extracts which were commonly used in traditional medicine, as alternative source of remedy (Kabir *et al.*, 2005). Medicinal principles are present in different parts of the plant like root, stem, bark, heartwood, leaf, flower, fruit or plant exudates. These medicinal principles are separated by different processes; the most common being extraction. Extraction is the separation of the required constituents from plant materials using a solvent. In the case of medicinal plants, the extraction procedure falls into two categories:

- a) Where it is sufficient to achieve within set limits equilibrium of concentration between drug components and the solution e.g. tinctures, decoction, teas, etc.
- b) Where it is necessary to extract the drug to exhaustion, i.e., until all solvent extractables are removed by the solvent.

Both the methods are employed depending on the requirement although in industry the latter method is mostly used. In all industrial procedures, the raw material is pre-treated with solvent outside the extractor before changing the latter. This prevents sudden bulk volume changes (which are the main cause of channelling during extraction) and facilitates the breaking up of the cell walls to release the extractables. To facilitate the extraction, the solvent should diffuse inside the cell and the substance must be sufficiently soluble in the solvent. The ideal solvent for complete extraction is one that is most selective, has the best capacity for extraction and is

compatible with the properties of the material to be extracted. These parameters are predetermined experimentally. The cost and availability of the solvent are also taken into account. Alcohol, though widely used, because of its great extractive power it is often the least selective, in that it extracts all soluble constituents. Alcohol in various ratios is used to minimize selectivity. The ideal alcohol ratio for woody or bark material is 75%. For leafy material, it is often less than 50% thus avoiding extraction of the chlorophyll which makes purification difficult. Experiment used for extraction with solvents usually comprise an extraction vessel with a heating jacket for steam heating or fitted with electrical devices, a condenser in reflux position, a solvent reservoir, a facility to convert to reboiler position or a separate reboiler and a short column for solvent recovery. Sometimes, sophisticated and costly equipment like the Carousel or the Inoxa extractor is employed (Joy *et al.*, 1998).

Technology for the manufacture of standardised extracts and phytochemicals is available and there are many extracts already in the international market as drugs. A drug such as an extract of *Centella asiatica* can be manufactured as an extract containing a standard quantity of asiaticoside. Similarly for senna a standardised extract of which, containing a standard quantity of sennosides a and b could easily be produced with equipment that can be designed and constructed in most developing countries (Wijesekera, 1991). The promotion and development of processing of medicinal and aromatic plants have gained momentum recently in many developing countries. Green consumerism and resurgence of interest for plant based products, liberalised and free market economy, increasing awareness about biodiversity conservation and sustainable use of natural resources coupled with poor socio-economic conditions of native populations are ground realities for planning and harnessing the low-cost and purpose oriented process technologies. UNIDO has developed a Polyvalent Pilot Plant with a view to enabling developing countries to upgrade their technology for the processing of medicinal and aromatic plants. This plant incorporates all salient features of a low cost, efficient, small capacity factory which can carry out solvent extraction, solvent percolation, concentration of miscella, solvent recovery, steam distillation and oil separation (Silva, 1997).

Conservation of Medicinal Plant Resources:

The world conservation strategy (IUCN, UNEP & WWF, 1980) defines conservation as "the management of human use of the biodiversity so that it may yield the greatest sustainable benefit to present generation while maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of future generations". The above definition invokes two complementary components "conservation" and "sustainability". Conserving forest biodiversity by valuing & harnessing it as medicine is consistent with poverty reduction and local public health prevention efforts. Global demand for herbal medicines is accompanied by dwindling supply of medicinal plants due to over-harvesting, habitat loss and agricultural encroachment. As millions of rural households use plants for self-medication and local herbalists are widespread, community involvement in monitoring use and status can contribute to effective strategies for sustainable use (Bodeker, 2005). The most widely accepted scientific technologies of biodiversity conservation are the *in-situ* and *ex-situ* methods. The strategies available for the conservation of medicinal and aromatic plants using both *in situ* and *ex situ* approaches, and making use of biotechnology tools are shown in following figure.

Fig. 1: Methods of conserving medicinal and aromatic plants (MAP) (Source: Natesh, 1997;2000)

In situ-conservation:

In order to conserve species that grow in the open or at the fringes of wooded areas or farms, *in situ* conservation methods should be supplemented with land use policies that would permit existence of such spots in either conservation areas or agricultural landscapes so that such specific species are conserved (Rao and Arora, 2004). The ultimate aim of *in situ* conservation of a species is to maintain a broad genetic diversity so that it can retain its potential to adapt to changes in the environment. A successful *in situ* gene conservation programme must fulfil three basic requirements (Koski *et al.* 1997):

- (1) Regeneration of the population must be assured and the new generation of trees must predominantly result from mating within the conserved population;
- (2) The number of genotypes in the conserved population must be large enough to include most of the common alleles;
- (3) The network of conserved stands must be distributed in such a way as to cover the spatial genetic variation present in the species.

Ex-situ Conservation:

The *ex situ* conservation methods may include growing the whole plants in field gene banks or by seed storage to conserve diversity. Appropriate seed storage technologies for different species have to be worked out and, at the same time, it should be made sure that the seeds planted produce plants of good quality comparable well with mother stock from which they were collected. Most of the medicinal plants that are selected and cultivated represent *ex situ* collections. While large numbers of plants are cultivated in a given area and the biomass used, it is necessary to compare once in a while, the quality of cultivated plants with those that were collected from nature (Rao and Arora, 2004). Efforts to propagate either by vegetative means or by using tissue culture which is becoming quite popular with many species (Gau *et al.* 1993), particularly those propagated vegetatively and are designated as endangered (Natesh, 2000; Rajasekharan and Ganeshan, 2002), requires testing of them on larger number of types of medicinal plants (or as accessions as we call them) as differences in genotypic responses exists and *ex situ* collections would be greatly useful in such situations. The development of propagation techniques (in addition to seed conservation, in cases where the seed produced is orthodox in nature and can be conserved under dry and cool conditions) such as tissue culture etc., can open doors for modern technologies for conservation such as *in vitro* conservation and cryopreservation. Such technologies not only increase the range of diversity that could be conserved, but also make the conservation efforts cost-effective and promote the utilization of the resources through safe exchange and propagation (Natesh, 1997; 2000).

Conservation and sustainable utilization of medicinal plants must necessarily involve a long term, integrated, scientifically oriented action programme. It need to be emphasized that biotechnology has opened new vista in the conservation of medicinal plants by way of: (i) rapid multiplication and reintroduction to nature of endangered species, (ii) assessment and monitoring of biodiversity as a source of new tools for conservation, and (iii) identification of new gene product potential use. Medicinal plants are potential renewable natural resources. Therefore, conservation of medicinal plant genetic resources will lead to better utilization of these important resources for human well being and health (Rao and Arora, 2004).

CONCLUSION

Plants provide a variety of resources that contribute to the fundamental needs of food, clothing and shelter. Among plants of economic importance medicinal and aromatic plants have played a vital role in alleviating human sufferings. Since times immemorial, medicinal plants have been used in virtually all cultures as a source of medicine. The global demand of herbal medicine is not only large but growing. Consequently, threat to genetic diversity of medicinal plants has increased as a result of habitat destruction, over-exploitation and other pressures as they are still being collected from the wild and exploited by humans unsustainably. Development of medicinal plants sector mainly depends on the awareness and interest of the farmers, supportive government policies, availability of assured markets, profitable price levels, and assess to simple and appropriate agro-techniques. The successful establishments of medicinal plants sector may help in raising rural employment, boost commerce around the world, and contribute to the health of millions.

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